

Nanoporous graphene constructed from nanoribbon superlattices with controllable pore morphology and size for wastewater treatment

Hazem Abdelsalam^{1,2*}, Mahmoud A. S. Sakr³, Vasil A. Saroka^{4,5,6}, Omar H. Abd-Elkader^{7*}, Qinfang Zhang^{1*}

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Yancheng Institute of Technology, Yancheng 224051, PR China

²Theoretical Physics Department, National Research Centre, El-Buhouth Str., 12622, Dokki, Giza, Egypt

³Center of Basic Science (CBS), Misr University for Science and Technology (MUST), 6th October City, Egypt.

⁴Department of Physics, University of Rome Tor Vergata and INFN, Via della Ricerca Scientifica 1, 00133, Roma, Italy

⁵Institute for Nuclear Problems, Belarusian State University, Bobruiskaya 11, 220030, Minsk, Belarus

⁶TBpack Ltd., 27 Old Gloucester Street, London WC1N 3AX, UK

⁷Department of Physics and Astronomy, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh 11451, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

The pollution of water bodies with toxic components possess a dangerous impact on human health and environment. Therefore, it is vital to find efficient materials for water treatment. Herein we construct various nanoporous graphene from nanoribbon superlattices with accurate control over pore size and active sites. The investigations are performed using density functional theory calculations. Depending on the type of the superlattice, the pore size can be tuned from 3 Å to 11 Å and the pore morphologies are also controllable. Some of the nanoporous graphenes have edge states at the zigzag terminations that decrease the band gap and act as active sites. While others do not have edge states due to the armchair terminations and form semiconductors with energy gap ~ 2.7 eV. Molecular electrostatic potential confirms that edge carbon atoms have high negative electronic densities and thus they are suitable for intermolecular coordination with the toxic metals. The considered 2D membranes show good capability to adsorb heavy metals, namely Cd, Pb, and Hg, with negligible deformation. Additionally, attaching chemical groups or elements, namely CN, COOH, CS₂, N, O, and S, to the pores not only increases the adsorption energy but also helps controlling the pore size. Therefore, with the enhanced adsorption energy and tunable pore size, the constructed nanoporous graphene are ideal candidates for 2D membranes.

Keywords: Nanoporous graphene; Nanoribbons superlattices; DFT; electronic properties; Heavy metals adsorption.

1. Introduction

Heavy metal ions are dangerous pollutants. Independently of the type of their source of origin, natural or industrial, they end up in the water and air environments and pose a long standing problem for human welfare [1–3]. This group of metals includes among others lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), zinc (Zn), mercury (Hg), arsenic (As), and even silver (Ag) and iron (Fe). Many heavy metal pollutants (As, Cd, Pb, and methylated forms of Hg) are poisonous even at low concentration. Such metals play no role in the human biochemistry and simply tend to bioaccumulation resulting in acute or chronic health problems. Environmental friendly, cost-efficient and scalable methods of removing and monitoring heavy metal ions in ecosystems are of great interest for creating safe environment worldwide [4].

Along with the conventional materials such as activated carbons [5], clay minerals [6], polymers [7], zeolites [8] and mesoporous materials [9], graphene-based nanomaterials have been proposed for effective heavy metal pollution treatment [10,11]. Large surface area, variety of compatible functional groups, and strong adsorption capacity are the main advantages of this group of materials. Among the range of treatment techniques for the elimination of heavy metal ions from waste water, membrane separation and sorption technology are standing out. The former demonstrates high separation efficiency, but high cost of maintenance in large scale applications. While the latter is easy to perform and relatively inexpensive, but requires improve in efficiency. Graphene oxide [10] and hexagonal boron nitride [12] quantum dots have been proposed as good adsorbents of heavy metals when functionalized with proper functional groups [13]. Although the parameters of nanocomposites with quantum dots such as selective functionalization, dot size and etc. are gradually improving, a strategic menace is problem with separation nanocomposites from aqueous solutions that affects recyclability, reversibility and reusability of these materials.

Similar to graphene sponges, aerogels and foams [11], graphene nanomeshes can overcome separation difficulties of traditional graphene-based adsorbents from aqueous solution after adsorption process. In contrast to nanometer size quantum dots, graphene nanomeshes are macroscopically large, integral and mechanically strong structures. As such they do not suffer from flocculation and aggregation. At the same time, they possess nanometer size pores and large edge area. Such structures have been already proposed for similar sieving applications such as water desalinization and gas separation [13–15]. The ionic and molecular nanofiltration with graphene nanomeshes is possible due to their ability to transport of water molecules while blocking solute ions or molecules; high water permeance of such ultrathin membranes with minimum transport resistance and maximum performance makes them an attractive for practical applications. Water permeance and the pore performance of the graphene nanomeshes are adjustable by the effective size and chemistry of the nanopores [16]. However, graphene nanomeshes are usually produced with O₂ plasma etching, where pore size and structure control is only coarsely feasible.

Graphene nanoribbons are nanometer width stripes of graphene [17–22]. They possess a range of attractive electronic [23–31], magnetic [24,32,33], optical [34–46], photovoltaic [47] and structural [48,49] properties. They exhibit astonishing structural variety of their edges that have been demonstrated to be achieved with atomic precision by means of bottom-up self-assembling of molecular precursors [50–52]. Over the past decade, a class of zigzag-shaped superlattices has expanded significantly. While the general classification of such structures is still a subject of future convention, the systematic classifications based on the ribbon edge morphology and superlattice parameters have been proposed [26,27,30]. The species of four major classes of zigzag-shaped superlattices have been synthesized: A60 [53–55], A120 [56–58], Z60 [59] and Z120 [60], where A and Z stand for the ‘armchair’ and ‘zigzag’ edge respectively, while 60 and 120 denote the apex angle that is characteristic for the zigzag shape of the structure [26,27,30]. In addition, the next level self-organization has been demonstrated, whereby self-assembled ribbons laterally fuse [57,58,60–62]. When fusing ribbons have straight edges or compatible symmetry along their axis of translation they tend to increase their width [58,60,61]. However, zigzag-like structures can form atomically perfect and ideally ordered pores [57,58]. Recently, the lateral fusion has been upraised to a totally different level and the atomically precise nanoporous membranes have been demonstrated [62], which made them competitive with macroscopically ordered azatriangulene-based [63] or boroxine-linked [64] covalent organic frameworks.

Our recent systematic study of the covalent organic frameworks (COF) have shown a promising potential for Cd, Hg, and Pb adsorption after functionalization with CN, COOH, and NO₂ [65]. Taking into account these results and recent advances in nanoporous graphene synthesis, we investigate the potential of currently available and perspective porous structures for the filtration of the water and air pollution detectors with respect to harmful heavy metal ions.

2. Computational model

In this study, a nanoporous graphene is modeled as a finite size system containing a sole pore of a regular shape. Here we focus on the in-pore chemistry and quantum properties of the pores, neglecting the macroscopic effects. This model should be valid for small and moderate concentrations of the heavy metals, when the active pores interacting with heavy metals can be considered to be independent and distributed non-periodically due to a stochastic nature of the interaction with atoms of metals. The calculations considered in this work were performed using density functional theory as implemented in Gaussian 16 [66]. The effective core potential “LANL2DZ” basis set was used to model the PG systems before and after adsorption of metals because it shows accurate description of the molecular properties of C-based materials before and after metal adsorption [67-69]. The functional used herein is the Becke-Three-Parameters-Lee-Yang-Parr hybrid functional (B3LYP) [70] since it shows a good representation of the electronic properties of C-based nanostructures [71,72]. The partial density of states was calculated using GaussSum software [73] based on the Gaussian output files.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Nanoporous graphene: construction and stability

In this work, we consider graphene nanoribbon superlattices with different width, length, and edge type to construct nanoporous graphene with tunable pore size and pore edges as presented in Fig. 1. The acronyms used in Fig. 1 are taken from our previous work on nanoribbon superlattices in Refs. [26,27,31,49]. Namely, A120-2-2 shown in Fig. 1 (a) means an armchair superlattice, where the apex angle equals 120° , width equals 2 benzene rings and length equals 2 unit cells [49]. A60-4-3 in Fig. 1 (b) represents armchair superlattice having an apex angle of 60° with width being equal to 4 dimer chains and length being equal to 3 unit cells [31]. Similarly, the Z120 and the narrow width Z120 (Z120-N) that are used to construct the nanoporous graphenes in Fig. 1 (e, f) can be found in Refs. [26, 27]. We are going also to investigate the recently synthesized nanoporous graphene with rubicene-type linkage of chevron graphene nanoribbons [62]. For porous structures we have chosen zigzag-shaped superlattices that have been demonstrated experimentally with large enough superlattice period, i.e. A60 [53–55], A120 [56–58], and Z120 [60]. Using such strategy, we can construct nanoporous graphenes with various pore sizes as demonstrated in Fig. 1 (c-g). For brevity, hereafter we refer to the constructed nanoporous graphenes using superlattice label supplemented with a ‘PG’ tag. For example, the nanoporous graphene constructed from A120-2-2 superlattice is denoted as A120-PG. Similar convention applies to other structures in question. When a pore edge is functionalized with a chemical group we include the chemical group into the label of the structure. If we use, for example, COOH group to modify the edge of A120-PG as shown in Fig. 1 (h), then the structure label is A120-PG-COOH. Figure 1 (h-j) demonstrates that further control over the pore size is obtained by attaching chemical groups.

The structure parameters such as the optimal bond length, bond angle, and dihedral angle are determined from the optimized A120-PG, A60-PG, Z120-PG, Z120-N-PG, and R-PG shown in Fig. 1. The C-H and C-C bond lengths fall between 1.079 Å to 1.509 Å. C-C-C bond angles also range from 116.70 to 124.14 degrees, and the C-C-C-C dihedral angle is around 180.00 degrees. The bond angles indicate that the type of hybridization is sp^2 . The dihedral angle values indicate that the surface of PGs is flat. The calculation of binding energy (E_b) per unit atom was performed using the equation $E_b = (N_C E_C + N_H E_H - E_t)/N_t$, where N_C , N_H , and N_t represent the number of carbon atoms, number of hydrogen atoms, and total number of atoms in the system, respectively. The total energies of the carbon atoms (E_C), hydrogen atoms (E_H), and the resultant compound (E_t) were used in the calculation. The values of E_b are 7.4, 7.2, 7.4, 7.6, and 7.7 eV for A120-PG, A60-PG, Z120-PG, Z120-N-PG, and R-PG, respectively. The positive values of E_b insure the stable formation of the considered PG systems. Notably, the E_b value for R-PG is the highest among the studied systems, suggesting that the R-PG is the most stable compared to the other structures. After functionalization, E_b are also positive with almost the same values as given in Table 1 which indicates that the PGs preserve their stability after chemical modification. Moreover, we perform frequency calculations to confirm the dynamical stability. The IR spectra for all the selected PGs show that all the vibrational frequencies responsible for the IR peaks are positive; see Fig. S1 of Appendix A. This indicates that there are no saddle points in the potential energy surface and all the structures are dynamically stable.

Fig. 1. The optimized structures of nanoribbon superlattices: (a) A120-2-2 and (b) A60-4-3. The finite 2D membranes with different pore sizes and edges constructed from the nanoribbon superlattices (c-g).

3.2 Electronic properties

Fig. 2 shows the electronic density of states (DOS) of the considered five nanoporous graphenes (a-e) and the corresponding distributions of the highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMO). The DOS are calculated using Gaussian distribution, $\frac{1}{\alpha\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp[-\frac{(\epsilon-\epsilon_i)^2}{2\alpha^2}]$ for each molecular orbital (ϵ_i) with broadening $\alpha = 0.032 \text{ eV}$. The finite 2D membranes considered here have different values of energy gaps: starting from 0.11 eV in R-PG to 2.73 eV in A120-PG. This difference in energy gaps in structures having almost the same number of atoms, such as A120-PG and A60-PG, is mainly a result of the edge type whether it is zigzag or armchair. The zigzag edges in graphene finite structures such as triangular nanographene hold unpaired electrons that cannot form pi- or sigma- bonds with neighbour C-atoms. Therefore, they form lower energy molecular orbitals that decreases the energy gap. It is worth noting that the values of energy gaps will be affected by considering spin-polarized calculations. However, since the main concern of this work is studying the adsorption capability of the nanoporous graphenes which is only slightly affected by spin-polarized calculations, we consider only the nonmagnetic calculations.

These half-filled edge states have been observed in all the considered systems, except for the A120-PG, and they are the reason for decreasing the energy gaps. The HOMO distribution can be used to understand the origin of bonds in that orbital. It can be delocalized on two C-atoms reflecting the origin from a pi-bond while a localized distribution indicates the origin from a lone pair or an unpaired electron on the atom. Since there are no lone pairs in the sp^2 hybridized graphene, then the localized distributions observed in all the considered nanoporous graphenes except for Z120-PG confirms their origin from the unpaired edge electrons, Fig. 2 (f-j). These edge electrons are highly interactive; thus they are promising for adsorption of heavy metals. On the other hand, nanoporous graphene with armchair terminations have all its electrons paired and the molecular orbitals distributions are extending on two or more atoms as seen in Fig. 2 (f) for HOMO distribution for A120-PG.

Fig. 2. Electronic density of states (a-e) of different nanoporous graphenes and the corresponding HOMO distributions (f-j).

3.3 Molecular electrostatic potentials

Molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) research, which is helpful for anticipating reaction sites, reveals the designed A120-PG, A60-PG, Z120-PG, Z120-N-PG, and R-PG electrophilic versus nucleophilic site. The MEPs are shown in Fig. 3. The color scheme of the MEP surface is as follows: red indicates an electron-rich, partially negative charge; blue indicates an electron-deficient, partially positive charge; light blue indicates an electron-deficient, slightly electron-rich region; yellow indicates an electron-rich, slightly positive region; and green indicates neutral (zero potential) (See Fig. 3). The presence of a negative region surrounding the carbon atoms indicates that electrophilic attacks are occurring there. Because all the hydrogen atoms are located in the positive region, it is possible for nucleophiles to target these sites. The neutral sections are the areas of the molecule where there is no charge distribution. All the molecular

structures that are studied showed that the carbon atoms located on the outer and inner boundaries have two sigma bonds with adjacent carbon atoms, while the carbon atoms located on the inside of the structures have three sigma bonds with adjacent carbon atoms. This results in higher negative electronic densities on the carbon atoms situated on the outer and inner boundaries than the carbon atoms on the inside. Therefore, the carbon atoms situated on the outer and inner boundaries are highly suitable for intermolecular coordination with toxic transition metals such as mercury (Hg^{+2}), lead (Pb^{+2}), and cadmium (Cd^{+2}) that are commonly present in contaminated water.

Fig. 3. Molecular electrostatic potential map (MEP) for A120-PG, A60-PG, Z120-PG, Z120-N-PG and R-PG using DFT/M06-2X/LANL2DZ level of theory.

3.4. PG-complexes with heavy metals

The A60-PG, A120-PG, Z120-PG, Z120-N-PG, and R-PG compounds were tested for their ability to complex with heavy metal ions (M^{+2}) such as Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} . Based on the MEP maps, the carbon atoms located on both the outer and inner boundaries exhibited a high potential for intermolecular coordination with toxic transition heavy metals. The results in Fig. 4 show that some of the complexes maintained a flat surface, while others were slightly deformed.

Fig. 4. The optimized structures of PG complexes with heavy metals (Top and side views).

The metal-PG bond distances for all PG-complexes were within the ranges of 2.433→4.896 Å. The Pb-C bond length was the shortest among A60-, A120-, Z120-, Z120-N-, and R-PG, as Pb forms chemical bonds comparing to the physical bonds by Hg and Cd. All PG complexes are stable and the process of adsorbing heavy metals by PG are successful as indicated by the negative values of the adsorption energy (E_{ads}). E_{ads} is defined as the difference between the ground state energy of the product (PG-metal) and reactants (PG and metals separately) with values ranging from -0.236 to -1.987 eV. The Pb-PG complexes had the highest negative E_{ads} values, indicating high stability compared to the other complexes. Due to Pb's small size, its adsorption to PG structures was higher than that of Hg and Cd, as confirmed by its more negative adsorption energy values compared to the other complexes.

3.5. Charge transfer analysis

The determination of atomic charges is crucial in understanding the electrical properties of molecular systems [2]. In this study, calculations were performed using the M06-2X/LanL2DZ level of theory to determine the natural atomic charge, natural population, and natural electronic configuration of metal ions in the studied PG complexes. The results in Table 1 indicate that the

computed charge on the metals is different than the zero formal charge due to interactions with The PG. The magnitude of charge transfer observed in Cd and Hg is considerably lower than that of Pb. Consequently, the affinity of Pb for PG is greater in comparison to Hg and Cd. Table 1 also provides the electronic configuration for Cd, Hg, and Pb ions in all PG- based compounds. It shows that Hg and Pb ions coordinate with carbon atoms of the PG group through the empty orbital 6p orbitals, while the Cd ion coordinates via the empty orbital 5p orbitals.

Table 1 Natural charge, population, and electronic configuration for PG complexes using B3LYP/LanL2DZlevel of theory.

Complexes	metal	Natural charge	Natural population				Natural electronic configuration
			Core	Valence	Rydberg	Total	
A60-PG	Cd	0.005	36	11.99	0.002	47.99	[core]5S ^(1.98) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
	Hg	-0.0002	68	11.99	0.002	80.00	[core]6S ^(1.99) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.01)
	Pb	1.12	78	2.87	0.004	80.87	[core]6S ^(1.88) 6p ^(0.99)
A120-PG	Cd	-0.007	36	12.00	0.002	48.00	[core]5S ^(2.00) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
	Hg	-0.005	68	12.00	0.002	80.00	[core]6S ^(2.00) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.01)
	Pb	0.716	78	3.28	0.004	81.28	[core]6S ^(1.93) 6p ^(1.35)
Z120-PG	Cd	0.016	36	11.98	0.003	47.98	[core]5S ^(1.97) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
	Hg	0.013	68	11.98	0.002	79.98	[core]6S ^(1.98) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.01)
	Pb	0.979	78	3.01	0.003	81.02	[core]6S ^(1.91) 6p ^(1.11)
Z120-N-PG	Cd	0.036	36	11.96	0.004	47.96	[core]5S ^(1.95) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
	Hg	0.028	68	11.96	0.003	79.97	[core]6S ^(1.95) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.02)
	Pb	0.981	78	3.016	0.003	81.01	[core]6S ^(1.91) 6p ^(1.11)
R-PG	Cd	-0.007	36	12.00	0.002	48.00	[core]5S ^(2.00) 4d ^(10.00) 5p ^(0.01)
	Hg	-0.005	68	12.00	0.002	80.00	[core]6S ^(2.00) 5d ^(10.00) 6p ^(0.01)
	Pb	0.937	78	3.05	0.004	81.06	[core]6S ^(1.96) 6p ^(1.10)

3.6. Chemical functionalization and adsorption

The effect of chemical functionalization, by attaching chemical groups to C-atoms inside the pores, is investigated because it is expected to have significant effects on the pore size and the adsorption capability of the constructed 2D membranes. Three nanopores are considered as examples for studying chemical functionalization, namely A120-PG, A60-PG, and R-PG. Since there are several ways to enhance the activity of a material by chemical functionalization such as oxidation (introducing oxygen containing groups, e.g. COOH, O, OH, etc.), nitrogenation, and sulfuration [74], we consider functionalization with COOH groups and O-atoms as examples of oxidation, CN and N for nitrogenation, and CS₂ and S for sulfuration. The impact of these functional groups on the binding energy of PGs is investigated by calculating the binding energy (E_b), similar to the case of nonfunctionalized PGs. The only difference is the addition of O, N, or S atoms energies multiplied by their number to E_b equation. The values of E_b obtained for each system are presented in Table 2, their positive values indicate that the PG-functional group systems are stable. Notably, R-PG-functional groups have the highest E_b value among the studied systems, suggesting that their molecular structure is the most stable. Additionally, the

positive vibrational frequencies of the IR spectra for chosen functionalized PG (Fig. S1 Appendix A) confirm the geometrical stability after chemical modification.

Table 2. Binding energy and energy gap of the chemically modified nanoporous graphene.

PG	E_b	E_g	PG	E_b	E_g
A120-PG-CN	7.41	2.64	A60-PG-O	7.22	0.22
A120-PG-N	7.39	1.42	A60-PG-S	7.20	0.23
A120-PG-COOH	7.39	2.66	A60-PG-CS ₂	7.19	0.19
A120-PG-O	7.40	0.18	R-PG-CN	7.69	0.11
A120-PG-S	7.39	0.21	R-PG-N	7.62	0.44
A120-PG-CS ₂	7.38	0.25	R-PG-COOH	7.68	0.11
A60-PG-CN	7.19	0.21	R-PG-O	7.67	0.60
A60-PG-N	7.20	0.36	R-PG-S	7.68	0.52
A60-PG-COOH	7.19	0.22	R-PG-CS ₂	7.67	0.17

The attached groups to C-atoms inside the pores have three main functions. (a) Tuning the electronic properties, for instance decreasing the energy gap and increasing the electron density around the Fermi level leads to a noticeable boost in the adsorption capability. (b) decreasing the pore size which in turn improves the sieving properties of the nanographene, for instance the large pore size of 11 Å in A120-PG can be decreased to 7 Å by attaching two COOH groups as seen in Fig. 1 (c, h). (c) enhancing the sorption capacity toward different pollutants by creating additional active sites. Starting by the electronic properties, the effect of chemical functionalization on the energy gap (Table 2) and the density of states (Fig. 5) show important modulations. The wide energy gap of A120-PG, $E_g=2.73$ eV, can be decreased to the half (1.42 eV) by attaching two N-atoms or significantly decreases to 0.18/0.25 eV by attaching O/CS₂ as given in Table. 1. In addition to the decrease of the energy gap, the electronic density of states shows a considerably increase of the intensity around the Fermi level for A120-PG after attaching CN and CS₂ groups (Fig. 5 a, b). These additional electronic states act as active sites that can bind with the pollutants and increase the adsorption energy. The decrease in the energy gap is not observed in the other membranes due to the existence of the low energy edge states which could be more interactive than the states from the attached chemical groups. However, the density of states increases by chemical functionalization, for instance the read peaks by the attached sulfur atoms in Fig. 5 (d).

Fig. 5. Electronic density of states of selected nanoporous graphenes that are chemically modified at the pore edges.

The effect of attaching the six chemical groups and elements on the adsorption of Cd by A60-PG is considered. The same is considered for the adsorption of Hg and Pb by A120-PG and R-PG, respectively. The results are divided into two parts, the first is shown in Fig. 6 and the second is shown in Fig. S2 Appendix B. The optimized structures of functionalized PGs after adsorption and the corresponding adsorption energies are depicted in Fig. 6. It is observed that the adsorption energy can be enhanced by chemical modification. For instance, the adsorption energy of Cd before functionalization ($E_{\text{ads}}=0.24$ eV) can be increased up to 0.67 eV by attaching nitrogen containing groups, see Fig. 6 (a). The adsorption of Hg slightly increases also by the

attached groups at the inner edges of A120-PG. The already high adsorption energy of Pb by R-PG ($E_{\text{ads}}=1.99$ eV) can be further increased to 3.37 eV by attaching CS₂ groups.

Fig. 6. The optimized structures (Front and side views) of functionalized PGs after adsorption of Cd (a-c), Hg (d-f), and Pb (g-h).

4. Conclusion

In summary, we construct various 2D nanoporous graphenes from nanoribbon superlattices with tunable pore size and morphology. The electronic properties of these 2D membranes and their interactions with heavy metals, Cd, Pb, and Hg, are investigated using DFT calculations. It is observed that the pore size can be smoothly controlled by changing the superlattice nanoribbons,

pores with sizes ranging from 3 Å to 11 Å are obtained. The pore morphology can be also controlled to have zigzag termination with interactive edge states suitable for complexation with pollutants or armchair (no edge states), or mixed edges. These edge states decrease the energy gap in some cases to 0.11 eV. While in other cases where these states disappear the nanoporous graphene is a semiconductor with an energy gap up to 2.7 eV. The molecular electrostatic potential confirms that the edge carbon atoms have higher negative electronic densities than surface ones, thus a higher probability of heavy metal adsorption. Nanoporous graphene successfully adsorbs different toxic metals with appropriate adsorption energy. Attaching chemical groups increases the active sites and provides additional control over the pore size. The adsorption strength can be further increased by attaching chemical groups to pore atoms. For instance, the adsorption energy of Cd is doubled by attaching nitrogen-containing groups.

Appendix A

The infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene shown in Fig. S1 indicate that there are no imaginary frequencies. This means that there are no saddle points and the structures correspond to a minimum on the B3LYP potential energy surface. Thus the considered systems are dynamically stable.

Fig. S1. The Infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene before and after chemical modification.

Appendix B

Fig. S2. presents the second part of complexes, in which the effect of chemical functionalization on the adsorption properties of PG toward Cd, Hg, and Pb. The calculated adsorption energy increases after chemical modification.

Fig. S2. The optimized structures and the adsorption energy of chemically functionalized-PGs after the adsorption of Cd (a-c), Hg (d-f), and Pb (g-i).

Acknowledgment

This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 12274361), the Ministry of Science and Technology, Foreign Experts Program (No. QN2021014007L, QN2022014009L), and the Natural Science Foundation of Jiangsu Province (BK20211361, 20KJA430004). This work is supported also by Researchers Supporting Project number (RSP2023R468), King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. VAS acknowledges support by EU HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01 (project no. 101065500, TeraExc).

Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

Conflict of Interest: The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest

Nanoporous graphenes

Adsorption of heavy metals

Conflict of Interest and Authorship Conformation Form

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Author's name	Affiliation
Hazem Abdelsalam	Yancheng Institute of Technology, China
Mahmoud A.S. Sakr	Misr University for science and technology, Egypt
Vasi Saroka	University of Rome Tor Vergata and INFN, Italy
Omar H. Abd-Elkader	King Saud University, Saudi Arabia
Qinfang Zhang	Yancheng Institute of Technology, China

Appendix A

The infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene shown in Fig. S1 indicate that there are no imaginary frequencies. This means that there are no saddle points and the structures correspond to a minimum on the B3LYP potential energy surface. Thus the considered systems are dynamically stable.

Fig. S1. The Infrared spectra of selected nanoporous graphene before and after chemical modification.

Appendix B

Fig. S2. presents the second part of complexes, in which the effect of chemical functionalization on the adsorption properties of PG toward Cd, Hg, and Pb. The calculated adsorption energy increases after chemical modification.

Fig. S2. The optimized structures and the adsorption energy of chemically functionalized-PGs after the adsorption of Cd (a-c), Hg (d-f), and Pb (g-i).